

Mapping Research Topics on Earning Per Share (EPS) in Sharia and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Earnings Per Share (EPS) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and literature review. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the EPS ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the EPS ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the EPS ratio using a literature review study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 103 journal publications regarding the EPS ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the EPS ratio are divided into 6 clusters and 168 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of literature review studies, there are 11 topics around the influence of the EPS ratio and 18 topics about the determinants of the EPS ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around EPS ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Earnings Per Share (EPS); Bibliometrics ; VOSviewer ; Literature Review ; Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

In the banking industry, the Earnings Per Share (EPS) ratio is used as an important measure in evaluating a company's financial performance. Along with the rapid growth of the banking industry, the use of the EPS ratio in assessing the performance of banking companies is also increasingly important. The EPS ratio can help investors and financial analysts to assess how much potential profit can be obtained from investing in banking companies. However, it is important to remember that banking has different business characteristics from other businesses. One of the differences is that banks have high leverage, that is, they use a lot of debt to finance their operations. Therefore, market conditions and external factors can quickly influence the financial performance of banking companies.

Apart from that, banks also face various risks such as credit risk, market risk and liquidity risk. Therefore, using the EPS ratio alone is not enough to assess the financial performance of banking companies. Banking companies must also use other financial ratios such as Return on Equity (ROE), Return on Assets (ROA), and Net Interest Margin (NIM) to obtain a more comprehensive picture of their financial performance. ROE measures how much profit a company generates per share invested by shareholders. ROA measures how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate profits. Meanwhile, NIM measures the difference between the interest income earned by a company from productive assets and the interest costs paid to finance these assets. In conclusion, although the EPS ratio is still an important measure in measuring the profitability of banking companies, it must

be used with caution and in a broader context. Apart from that, banking companies must also use other financial ratios to obtain a more comprehensive picture of their financial performance.

There are various studies that have been conducted to study the use of the EPS ratio in banking. Several of these studies discuss the factors that influence the EPS ratio, as well as the relationship between the EPS ratio and the financial performance of banking companies. First, there is research that identifies several factors that influence the EPS ratio in banking companies in India. This research shows that factors such as Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and interest rates influence the EPS ratio in banking companies in India. Second, other research discusses the relationship between the EPS ratio and the financial performance of banking companies in Indonesia. This research shows that the EPS ratio has a significant relationship with Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) in banking companies in Indonesia. Third, research shows that the use of the EPS ratio together with other financial ratios such as Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Net Interest Margin (NIM) can provide more comprehensive information about the financial performance of banking companies. Overall, research on the use of the EPS ratio in banking shows that this ratio is still an important measure in assessing the financial performance of banking companies. However, the EPS ratio must be used in conjunction with other financial ratios to obtain a more comprehensive picture of a banking company's financial performance. Apart from that, research also shows that factors such as ROA, ROE, and interest rates can influence the EPS ratio in banking companies.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around EPS in Sharia and Conventional Banking by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding EPS. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research EPS. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics regarding the EPS ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Earnings Per Share (EPS) is a ratio that measures how much net profit per share is available to company shareholders. EPS is often used as an indicator of company profits and financial performance. For banks, EPS measures how much net profit a bank generates per share that is available to shareholders. This EPS is calculated by dividing banking net profit by the number of shares circulating on the market. However, EPS calculations in banks can be slightly different from companies in general. This is because banks usually have financial instruments such as bonds and preferred shares which have rights to profits before ordinary shareholders. So, to calculate EPS in banking, net profit needs to be calculated after taking into account the rights to profits from the financial instruments.

Bibliometric studies constitute research method that uses bibliographic data (information about scientific publications) and statistics to measure and analyze scientific publications in a particular field or topic. In bibliometric studies, the bibliographic data used usually comes from citation indexes, such as Web of Science or Scopus, which provide information about the number of citations, impact factor, and frequency of publication in a particular journal. Then, this data is analyzed and interpreted to produce information about trends and patterns of

scientific publications in a field, as well as identifying authors, journals or institutions that have contributed the most to that field. Bibliometric studies are often used to assist decision making in developing research and development strategies in various fields, such as science, technology, medicine, and social sciences. Bibliometric studies are also often used as an indicator of research quality in evaluating the academic performance of institutions or individual researchers.

VOSviewer is open source software used to visualize and analyze bibliometric data. This software can help users to identify patterns and trends in bibliometric data, such as citation patterns, collaboration between authors, and networks of relationships between keywords. In VOSviewer, bibliometric data such as citations, keywords, or author affiliation, can be imported from various bibliometric data sources, such as Web of Science or Scopus. Once the data is imported, users can create various types of visualizations, such as three-dimensional maps, network graphs, or cluster maps. This visualization can help users to identify patterns and relationships between various elements in bibliometric data. Apart from that, VOSviewer can also perform bibliometric analysis, such as keyword linkage analysis or cluster analysis. This analysis can help users to understand trends and patterns in the resulting bibliometric data. VOSviewer is a popular and frequently used software in the fields of bibliometrics and information science.

Studies literature review is research methods used to collect, evaluate, and synthesize research that has been previously conducted in a particular field or topic. The purpose of a literature review study is to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the topic being researched and gain a deeper understanding of the theory and practice related to the topic. In a literature review study, researchers will search for, identify, and evaluate various literature sources, such as journal articles, books, research reports, and other sources related to the topic under study. After that, the researcher will compile and analyze these sources to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the topic under study. Literature review studies can be conducted as part of primary research or as independent research. Literature review studies can help researchers to identify gaps in previous research, develop a strong theoretical framework, and determine the most appropriate research methods to conduct on the topic under study. Literature review studies can also help to determine better and clearer research direction and focus.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The research object is Earnings Per Share (EPS). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on EPS in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for accredited national journals, Sinta via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keywords " Earnings Per Share " and " EPS" for the entire year; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Software visualization results VOSViewer related to the research development map regarding the EPS ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, there are 6 clusters and 168 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1, consists of 37 topic items, namely : annual financial statement, assets, bank Indonesia, beverage company, company size, current ratio, data analysis technique, development, effect, exchange rate, financial performance, financial report, firm size, idx, indonesia stock exchange, mining company, moderated regression analysis, moderating variables, mra, multiple linear regression, multiple regression analysis, negative effect, path analysis, price book value, profit, profitability, purposive sampling method, ratio, relationship, significant influence, significant negative positive effect, SPSS program, stock return.
- Cluster 2, consists of 35 topic items, namely: analysis of the influence of earnings, operating cash flow, banking company, bei, book value, Indonesian stock exchange, cash flow, earningsinig, economic value added, Indonesian effects, eps, eva, eviws, price shares, market value added, analysis methods, MVA, influence of earning returns, per company, price earning ratio, purposive sampling, stock returns, ROI, share, significant on stock prices/returns, software, t test.
- Cluster 3, consists of 34 topic items, namely: autocorrelation test, classical assumption test, coefficient, data analysis method, determination, equity and earnings, f table, f test, financial statement, form, heteroscedasticity test, hypothesis testing, insignificant effect, multicollinearity test, multiple linear regression, normality test, partial test, regression model, research model/data, secondary data, share variable, significance value/effect, simultaneous test, stock price, t test, tbk, test result, type.
- Cluster 4, consists of 29 topic items, namely: analytical method, capital, company value, dividend policy, dps, earnings per share, firm value, hypothesis, increase, investment decision, leverage, lq45 index, manufacturing company, moderating variable, multiple linear regression, pbv, performance, population, positive effect, profitability ratio, purposive sampling technique, quantitative research, research sample, share in stock price, significant impact, stock exchange, total sample.
- Cluster 5, consists of 18 topic items, namely: capital market, data analysis, influence, information, investment, investor, net profit margin, npm, property, quantitative approach, real estate, research method, roa, roe, share price, significance level, spss.
- Cluster 6, consists of 15 topic items, namely: analysis technique, classical assumption, criteria, debt, der, dividend payout ratio, dpr, equity ratio, hypothesis test, independent variable, multiple regression, partial regression coefficient, sampling method/technique, total asset turnover.

Mapping Literature Review Studies around the Influence of Earnings Per Share (EPS) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 11 influences of EPS on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, audit delay. Audit delay is the time required by companies to complete their financial audits after the fiscal year ends. Usually, the longer the audit delay, the worse the quality of the company's financial reports. EPS can affect audit delay because companies must ensure that their financial statements reflect actual performance and include all relevant revenues and costs to produce accurate EPS.

Therefore, the higher the EPS, the more likely a company will take longer to complete their financial audits to ensure the accuracy of their financial statements.

Second, Bid-ask spreads. The bid-ask spread is the difference between the bid price and the ask price of a stock in the market. The higher the bid-ask spread, the more difficult it is for investors to buy or sell shares at the desired price, and the more difficult it is for companies to raise capital through the capital markets. EPS can affect the bid-ask spread because the higher the EPS, the higher the demand for investors to buy the company's shares. In this case, the bid-ask spread will tend to narrow because more investors are willing to buy company shares, making it easier for the company to obtain capital through the capital market.

Third, share prices. The share price is the market value of a company's shares which is reflected in the share price on the capital market. EPS can influence share prices because the higher the EPS, the more likely it is that investors will buy the company's shares. Investments that promise high returns in the long term tend to be more attractive to investors, so high EPS can increase demand for shares and directly influence share prices. However, other factors such as economic fundamentals, company policies, and market factors can also influence stock prices.

Fourth, stock holding period. A stock holding period is the time period an investor holds company shares before selling them. EPS can affect a stock's holding period because the higher the EPS, the more likely investors will tend to maintain their investment in the long term. This is because high EPS shows good company performance and increases investor confidence in the company. Conversely, low EPS may cause investors to consider selling their shares in the short term to avoid greater risks.

Fifth, inflation. Inflation is a general increase in the prices of goods and services in an economy over a certain period of time. EPS can influence inflation because high EPS can indicate that the company is growing and generating greater profits. This can increase consumer demand and encourage increases in prices of goods and services in the market. However, the relationship between EPS and inflation is not always consistent because other factors such as demand and supply, political stability, and monetary policy can also influence inflation.

Sixth, dividend policy. Dividend policy is a company's policy in distributing its net profits to shareholders in the form of dividends. EPS can influence dividend policy because the higher the EPS, the greater the possibility that the company will pay larger dividends to shareholders. Banking companies usually distribute stable and high dividends, therefore high EPS can increase investor confidence in the company and encourage companies to pay higher dividends.

Seventh, company value. Company value is the total value measured from all company assets, including the stock market value. EPS can influence company value because the higher the EPS, the greater the possibility that investors will buy shares in the company and directly influence the share market value. High EPS can also indicate good company performance and increase investor confidence in the company, which can also affect company value.

Eighth, state-owned companies. BUMN companies are companies owned by the state and usually have an important role in the national economy. EPS can influence the performance of state-owned companies in banking because the higher the EPS, the greater the possibility that the company will be able to make a greater contribution to the national economy. High EPS can indicate good performance and increase public trust in state-owned companies, which can also influence the company's performance in the future.

Ninth, stock returns. Stock returns are the returns investors receive from their stock investments. EPS can influence stock returns because the higher the EPS, the greater the possibility that investors will buy shares in the company and

this directly influences the share price. High EPS can also indicate good company performance and increase investor confidence in the company, which can also influence stock returns.

Tenth, company size. Company size is a measure that measures how big or small a company is. EPS can affect company size because the higher the EPS, the greater the possibility that the company will grow and become bigger in the market. High EPS can also indicate good company performance and increase investor confidence in the company, which can also influence company size.

Eleventh, absolute real and absolute timeliness after the publication of auditing financial statement. EPS is a financial ratio that measures a company's profit per share outstanding. EPS does not have a direct influence on real and absolute timeliness after the publication of auditing financial statements in banking. However, EPS can provide important information about a company's financial performance which can influence company management decisions in releasing financial reports. Real absolute timeliness refers to the time required to complete an audit and release financial reports. Absolute timeliness after the publication of auditing financial statements refers to the time it takes investors and financial analysts to analyze newly released financial statements. High EPS can indicate good company performance, which can influence management decisions in releasing financial reports quickly and providing accurate information about the company's financial performance. Apart from that, high EPS can also increase investor confidence in the company and encourage investors and financial analysts to analyze financial reports quickly, which can affect the absolute timeliness after the publication of auditing financial statements. However, the influence of EPS on real and absolute timeliness after the publication of auditing financial statements cannot be concluded in general due to differences between each company and other factors that influence management and financial analyst decisions. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out further research to clarify the relationship between EPS and real absolute timeliness and ABS results after the publication of auditing financial statements in banking.

Study Mapping Literature Review regarding Determinant Variables of Earnings Per Share/EPS in Sharia and Conventional Banking

literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 18 EPS determinant variables in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, cash flow/operating cash flow. Cash flow/operating cash flow is cash inflow from the company's operational activities which is the main source for financing the company's activities. Increasing cash flow/operating cash flow can have a positive impact on a company's EPS, because the company can use these funds to finance its operational activities, increase operational efficiency, and invest for business growth. This can increase the company's net profit and ultimately strengthen the company's EPS.

Second, cash dividends. Cash dividend is a dividend payment made in the form of cash to shareholders. Dividend payments made by a company can affect the company's EPS. If a company pays large cash dividends, this can reduce the amount of net income available to reinvest in the company. Conversely, if the company does not pay dividends or only pays small dividends, then the net profit available to reinvest in the company will increase, which can increase the company's EPS.

Third, current ratio. Current ratio is a financial ratio that measures a company's ability to meet its short-term obligations using current assets. An increase in the current ratio can increase investor and creditor confidence in the company's finances, because it shows the company's ability to fulfill its short-term obligations. This can strengthen the company's position in the market and increase company profits, which in turn can strengthen the company's EPS.

Fourth, Covid-19. The Covid-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on various economic sectors, including the banking sector. In some cases, the Covid-19 pandemic can affect banking performance and company EPS. For example, the Covid-19 pandemic can cause a decrease in revenue and increased credit risk for banks, which can reduce company EPS. However, on the other hand, banks can also take advantage of opportunities in this situation, such as increased demand for online banking services or better credit risk management, which can increase company EPS.

Fifth, Debt to Equity/DER. DER is a financial ratio that measures the level of use of debt and own capital in funding a company. A high DER level can indicate that the company is utilizing debt more than its own capital, which can increase financial risk and reduce the company's EPS. Conversely, a low DER level can indicate that the company uses more own capital than debt, which can increase investor and creditor confidence and increase the company's EPS.

Sixth, Dividend Payout Ratio/DPR. DPR is a ratio that measures how much net profit is distributed as dividends to shareholders. An increase in the Dividend Payout Ratio can cause a reduction in net income available to reinvest in the company, which can reduce the company's EPS. Conversely, if the Dividend Payout Ratio is low, the net profit available to reinvest in the company will increase, which can increase the company's EPS.

Seventh, Gross Profit Margin/GPM. GPM is a financial ratio that measures a company's gross profit as a percentage of revenue. A high GPM shows that the company is able to generate higher profits from sales, which can increase the company's EPS. Conversely, a low GPM indicates that the company is generating less profit from sales, which can reduce the company's EPS.

Eighth, inventory turnover. Inventory Turnover is a ratio that measures how quickly a company converts inventory into sales. A high level of Inventory Turnover shows that the company is efficient in managing inventory and maximizing its use in sales, which can increase the company's EPS. Conversely, low Inventory Turnover can indicate that the company is inefficient in managing inventory and cannot generate enough sales, which can reduce the company's EPS.

Ninth, leverage. Leverage is a ratio that measures how much a company uses borrowed funds (debt) to finance its business operations. Leverage can affect EPS because the use of debt can have a leverage effect on company profits. However, if the company relies too much on debt, the interest that must be paid will eat up a large part of net profit, causing EPS to decrease. Therefore, banking companies must pay attention to their leverage levels so that they are not too high and reduce the risk of bankruptcy.

Tenth, Net Profit Margin/NPM. NPM is a ratio that measures how large a percentage of a company's revenue becomes net profit. NPM can affect EPS because the higher the NPM, the more profit the company generates. Thus, EPS will increase. However, if the NPM is too low, the profit generated will be small and can cause EPS to decrease. Banking companies must strive to maintain a healthy NPM in order to maximize their EPS.

Eleventh, net sales. Net sales are total sales after deducting returns, discounts and other sales costs. Net sales can affect EPS because the higher the net sales, the more income the company earns. Thus, EPS will increase. However, if net sales are too low, then the income earned will be small and can cause EPS to decrease. Banking companies should try to increase their net sales by increasing the number of customers or offering new products.

Twelfth, Operating Profit Margin/OPM. OPM is a ratio that measures how large a percentage of a company's revenue becomes operational profit. OPM can affect EPS because the higher the OPM, the more profit the company generates. Thus, EPS will increase. However, if OPM is too low, the profit generated will be

small and can cause EPS to decrease. Banking companies must strive to maintain a healthy OPM by reducing operational costs or increasing operating income.

Thirteenth, Price to Book Value/PBV. PBV is a ratio that measures the comparison between a company's share price and book value per share. PBV can affect EPS because the higher the PBV, the higher the company's value on the stock market and the greater investor confidence in the company. This can encourage investors to buy company shares, thereby increasing EPS. However, if PBV is too high, then the company's shares are considered overvalued and investors may sell their shares, which can cause EPS to decrease.

Fourteenth, Return On Assets/ROA. ROA is a ratio that measures how large a percentage of a company's total assets generate net profit. ROA can affect EPS because the higher the ROA, the more efficient the company is in generating profits from their assets. Thus, EPS will increase. However, if ROA is too low, the profit generated will be small and can cause EPS to decrease. Banking companies should strive to increase their ROA by maximizing the use of their assets.

Fifteenth, Return On Equity/ROE. ROE is a ratio that measures how much net profit a company generates compared to shareholder equity. ROE can affect EPS because the higher the ROE, the more efficient the company is in generating profits for shareholders. Thus, EPS will increase. However, if ROE is too low, the profit generated will be small and can cause EPS to decrease. Banking companies should strive to increase their ROE by improving operational efficiency or increasing return on investment.

Sixteenth, company size. Company size, in this case measured by total assets, can influence EPS because the bigger the company, the greater the potential income that can be generated and the greater the opportunity to reduce operational costs. However, large companies can also face challenges in maintaining efficiency and taking on greater risks. Therefore, banking companies must consider the benefits and risks associated with their size.

Seventeenth, company age. A company's age can affect EPS because more mature and established companies may have a better reputation and greater market opportunities, which can increase investor confidence and result in increased EPS. However, newly founded companies may be able to benefit from greater innovation and flexibility in the face of market changes. Therefore, it is important for banking companies to consider the advantages and disadvantages associated with their lifespan.

Eighteenth, Total Asset Turnover/TATO. TATO is a ratio that measures how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate income. TATO can affect EPS because the higher this ratio, the more income is generated from each dollar of assets used. Thus, EPS will increase. However, if TATO is too low, then the company may not use its assets efficiently and may generate less revenue, which can cause EPS to decrease.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on the mapping of the distribution of journal publications regarding the Earnings Per Share (EPS) ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2007 to 2022 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 103 published journal articles. Second, based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the EPS ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking are divided into 6 clusters and 168 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 37 topics, cluster 2 consists of 35 topics, cluster 3 consists of 34 topics, cluster 4 consists of 29 topics, cluster 5 consists of 18 topics, and cluster 6 consists of 15 topics. Third, based on mapping studies literature review, there are 11 topics related to the influence of the EPS ratio on Sharia and Conventional

Banking, namely: audit delay, bid-ask spreads, stock prices, stock holding period, inflation, dividend policy, company value, state-owned companies, stock returns, company size, and absolute timeliness real and absolute after the publication of auditing financial statement. And there are 18 topics related to the determinants of the EPS ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: cash flow/operating cash flow, cash dividend, current ratio, covid-19, Debt to Equity/DER, Dividend Payout Ratio/DPR, Gross Profit Margin/GPM, inventory turnover, leverage, Net Profit Margin/NPM, net sales, Operating Profit Margin/OPM, Price to Book Value/PBV, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, company size, company age, and Total Asset Turnover/TATO.

Suggestion

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, both from national accredited journals Sinta and international journals indexed by Scopus, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer time span for research data so that it can The following research results were obtained: first, it is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization. Second, the study results literature The review can be explained in a more complex way.

References

- Abidin, U. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Third-Party Fund (DPK) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117572>
- Aini, A. P. N., Salsabilla, L. Z., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Compilation of Sharia Economic Law (KHES): Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117521>
- Aini, A. P. N., Salsabilla, L. Z., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Kompilasi Hukum Ekonomi Syariah (KHES): Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078577>
- Al-Fattah, M. F., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Islamic and Conventional Mutual Funds (Reksa Dana): Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117306>
- Al-Fattah, M. F., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Reksa Dana Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078579>
- Al-Ghozy, H. R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Musaqah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117769>
- Amaliani, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Income Smoothing (Perataan Laba) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078569>
- Amaliani, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Income Smoothing on*

- Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117537>
- Amin, S. M. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Garansi pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077304>
- Amin, S. M. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Guarantees on Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117749>
- Andresta, T., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Muamalat Indonesia: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117698>
- Andresta, T., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Muamalat Indonesia: Studi Pustaka (Library Research).* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077344>
- Anggreni, L. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *National Sharia Arbitration Agency (BASYARNAS): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117655>
- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Ijarah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117783>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Literature Review Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Risiko Operasional pada Industri Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ekonomi Islam*, 14(2), 158–174. <https://doi.org/10.22236/jei.v14i2.11121>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Risiko Reputasi pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada

- Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Research Mapping on Credit Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Danamon Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117751>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Danamon Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077292>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117611>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Cash Ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117607>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117603>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Current Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117601>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117564>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Dividend Per Share in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117548>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Economic Value Added (EVA) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117545>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Financial Value Added (FVA) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117539>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Financing Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117292>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Jualah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117779>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Mapping Research on the Ratio of Operating Costs to Operating Income (BOPO) in Sharia and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117623>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Net Operating Margin (NOM) on Islamic Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117324>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Net Profit Margin (NPM) Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117320>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Non Performing Financing (NPF) on Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117318>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAFTA (Journal of Accounting, Finance, Taxation & Auditing)*, 4(2), 32–53. <https://doi.org/10.28932/jafta.v4i2.7650>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik

- VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio On Investment (ROI) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Kompetensi (Competence: Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Total Asset Turnover (TATO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Manajemen*, 20(2), 40–53. <https://doi.org/10.36406/jam.v20i2.975>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Reputation Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117288>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Research Mapping the Operating Profit Margin (OPM) Ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117316>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Return On Investment (ROI) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117286>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharf on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117759>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *The Influence of Book Value per Share (BVS) on Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117619>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Total Asset Turnover (TATO) on Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10142629>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Working Capital Turnover (WCT) Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117154>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional:

- Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Literature Review. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Cahyaningrum, D., Hariyono, H. N. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Guarantees/Collateral in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117529>
- Cahyaningrum, D., Hariyono, H. N. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Jaminan/Agunan pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078573>
- Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). *The Influence of Macroeconomic Variables: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117329>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Elkhori, N. E. M., Safira, W. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Denda pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078519>
- Emiliani, E., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Hawala on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117785>
- Faiz, M. W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Safe Deposit Box pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078581>
- Fajaryati, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Mega Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117747>
- Fajaryati, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Mega Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077317>
- Farida, M., Andriani, H. L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Subrogasi pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078583>

- Farida, M., Andriani, H. L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Subrogation in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117160>
- Fauzan, I. F. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117745>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). *Pengaruh Pengetahuan, Kepercayaan, Produk, Pelayanan, dan Religiusitas terhadap Minat Menabung*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117278>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). The Effect of Knowledge, Trust, Products, Services and Religiosity on Interest in Saving. *The 9th International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business (ICONIES 2023)*, 85–96. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037033>
- Febriyanti, R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and Bibliometrics VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117743>
- Febriyanti, R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Panin Dubai Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077588>
- Fikri, U. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Pembangunan Daerah (BPD) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077610>
- Fikri, U. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharia and Conventional Regional Development Banks (BPD): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117690>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *The Influence of Return On Equity (ROE) in Islamic Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117294>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Equity (ROE) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Hidayat, R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Victoria Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117712>
- Hidayat, R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Victoria Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078459>
- Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Zakah*

- Management in Islamic Financial Institutions: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117328>
- Laksana, E. Y., Rusydi, F. N., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS) in Islamic Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117554>
- Laksana, Y. E., Rusydi, F. N., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Dewan Pengawas Syariah (DPS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078565>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharia and Conventional National Pension Savings Bank (BTPN): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117662>
- Muna, R. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117678>
- Muna, R. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI): Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078436>
- Nursaputri, D. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Muzara'ah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117767>
- Panatagama, A. R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Wakalah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117755>
- Prayogi, A. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Permata Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117740>
- Prayogi, A. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Permata Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10077628>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117655>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Murabaha on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117771>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics.*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117670>

- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Rahn (Pawn) on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117763>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Wadi'ah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117757>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Maybank Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117627>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Maybank Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank CIMB Niaga Sharia and Conventional on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117629>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): *JEMPER Januari-Juni*, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmah, R. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *The Application of Financial Accounting Standard Statements (PSAK) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117314>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Research Mapping around the Determinant Variables of Return on Assets (ROA) in Islamic Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117298>
- Saputra, H. M. G. A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives (KJKS): Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117332>
- Saputri, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Internet Banking in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer*

Bibliometric and Library Research.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117533>

- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Salam on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117761>
- Suwandini, F. K. T., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Islamic Rural Banks (BPRS): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometric.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117684>
- Syarifah, H. L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Qard on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117765>
- Ummah, F. K., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Fatwa Dewan Syariah Nasional Majelis Ulama Indonesia (DSN-MUI) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078567>
- Wulandari, D. R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Central Asia (BCA) Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and Bibliometrics VOSviewer.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117704>
- Wulandari, D. R., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Central Asia (BCA) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10075718>
- Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Istisna' on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117781>